

PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO EGO CHARACTERISTICS

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Аннотация: Ushbu maqolada ego xususiyatlari, uning yosh davrlarida namoyon bo‘lishi va uning ko‘rinishlari, shuningdek egoizmga oid nazariy qarashlar, tahlil etilgan fikrlar baton etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: tahlil, ego-holat, g‘amxo‘r ota-onalar, moslashish, mustaqillik, erkin fikrli bola, yutuqlarga erishish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается наличие взаимосвязи между расширенными ego-состояниями (предложенными в теории транзактного анализа) и мотивацией личности на успех.

Ключевые слова: транзактный анализ, эго-состояния, заботливый родитель, адаптивный ребенок, свободный ребенок, мотивация успеха

Abstract: The article considers the existence of the relationship between extended ego states (proposed in the theory of transactional analysis) and the motivation of the individual to succeed.

Keywords: transactional analysis, ego states, caring parent, adaptive child, free child, motivation for success

Ego psychology: the result of the development of psychoanalysis Erikson’s theoretical formulations relate exclusively to the development of the I (ego). Although he consistently insisted that his ideas were nothing more than a further systematic development of Freud’s concept of psychosexual development in the light of new discoveries in the social and biological sciences, Erikson decisively departed from classical psychoanalysis on four important points. First, his work clearly shows a decisive shift in emphasis from the id to the ego, which Freud himself only partially recognized in the last years of his activity. From Erikson’s perspective, it is rather the Self that forms the basis of human behavior and functioning. He considered the Self as an independent personality structure, the main direction of development of which is social adaptation; In parallel, the development of the id and instincts occurs. This view of human nature, called ego psychology, differs radically from early psychodynamic thinking in that ego psychology describes people as more rational

and therefore making conscious decisions and consciously solving life's problems. While Freud believed that the ego struggled to resolve the conflict between instinctual drives and moral constraints, Erikson argued that the self is an autonomous system that interacts with reality through perception, thinking, attention and memory. Paying special attention to the adaptive functions of the self, Erickson believed that a person, interacting with the environment in the process of his development, becomes more and more competent.

Second, Erikson develops a new perspective regarding the individual's relationship with parents and the cultural context in which the family exists. If Freud was interested in the influence of parents on the development of the child's personality, then Erikson emphasizes the historical conditions in which the child's self is formed. It draws on observations of people belonging to different cultures to show that the development of the self is inevitably and closely related to the changing characteristics of social prescriptions and value systems.

Third, the theory of self development covers the entire life space of an individual (that is, from infancy to adulthood and old age). Freud, on the contrary, limited himself to the influence of early childhood experiences and did not pay attention to issues of development beyond the genital stage.

And finally, fourthly, Freud and Erikson have different views on the nature and resolution of psychosexual conflicts. Freud's goal was to reveal the essence and characteristics of the influence of unconscious mental life on the individual, as well as to explain how early trauma can lead to psychopathology in adulthood. Erikson, on the contrary, saw his task as drawing attention to a person's ability to overcome life's difficulties of a psychosocial nature. His theory prioritizes the qualities of the Self, that is, its advantages, which are revealed during various periods of development. Perhaps this last distinction is key to understanding Erikson's concept of organization and personal development. Freud's fatalistic warning that people are doomed to social decline if they give in to their instinctual aspirations is countered by the optimistic position that every personal and social crisis represents a kind of challenge that leads the individual to personal growth and overcoming life's obstacles. Knowing how a person dealt with each of life's significant problems, or how inadequate handling of early problems left him unable to deal with later problems, is, according to Erikson, the only key to understanding his life.

So far we have touched only on the main theoretical differences between Erikson and Freud. However, it is worth noting that there are also issues on which there is agreement between them. For example, both theorists agree that the stages of

personality development are predetermined, and the order of their passage is unchanged. Erikson also recognizes the biological and sexual basis of all later motivational and personality dispositions, and also accepts the Freudian structural model of personality (Id, Ego, Superego). However, despite the presence of similar provisions, many personologists believe that Erikson's theoretical premises differ from those in classical psychoanalysis. Epigenetic principle Central to the theory of self development created by Erikson is the position that a person during his life goes through several stages that are universal for all humanity. The unfolding of these stages is regulated according to the epigenetic principle of maturation. By this Erickson means the following:

"1) in principle, the personality develops stepwise, the transition from one stage to another is predetermined by the individual's readiness to move in the direction of further growth, expansion of the conscious social horizon and the radius of social interaction;

2) society, in principle, is structured in such a way that the development of a person's social capabilities is accepted approvingly, society attempts to promote the continuation of this trend, and to maintain both the proper pace and the correct sequence of development" (Erikson, 1963a, p. 270). In *Childhood and Society* (1963a), Erikson divided human life into eight distinct stages of psychosocial development of the self (as they say, the "eight ages of man"). According to him, these stages are the result of an epigenetically unfolding "personal blueprint" that is inherited genetically. The epigenetic concept of development (in Greek "???" means "after", and "???????" - "birth, origin") is based on the idea that each stage of the life cycle occurs at a specific time for it. time ("critical period"), and also that a fully functioning personality is formed only by passing through successively all stages in its development. In addition, according to Erikson, each psychosocial stage is accompanied by a crisis - a turning point in the life of an individual, which arises as a consequence of achieving a certain level of psychological maturity and social demands placed on the individual at this stage. In other words, each of the eight phases of the human life cycle is characterized by an evolutionary task specific to this particular phase ("phase-specific") - a problem in social development, which at one time is presented to the individual, but does not necessarily find its solution. An individual's characteristic patterns of behavior are determined by how each of these tasks is ultimately resolved or how a crisis is overcome. Conflict plays a vital role in Erikson's theory because growth and expansion of the scope of interpersonal relationships is associated with increasing vulnerability of self functions at each

stage. At the same time, he notes that crisis means “not the threat of catastrophe, but a turning point, and thereby an ontogenetic source of both strength and insufficient adaptation” (Erikson, 1968, p. 286). Each psychosocial crisis, when viewed from an assessment point of view, contains both positive and negative components. If the conflict is resolved satisfactorily (that is, at the previous stage the I was enriched with new positive qualities), then now the I absorbs a new positive component (for example, basal trust and independence), and this guarantees the healthy development of the personality in the future. On the contrary, if the conflict remains unresolved or is unsatisfactorily resolved, the developing self is thereby harmed and a negative component is built into it (for example, basal mistrust, shame and doubt).

Although theoretically predictable and well-defined conflicts arise along the path of personality development, it does not follow from this that at the previous stages successes and failures are necessarily the same. The qualities that the self acquires at each stage do not reduce its susceptibility to new internal conflicts or changing conditions (Erikson, 1964a). The goal is for the individual to adequately resolve each crisis so that he or she will be able to approach the next stage of development as a more adaptive and mature individual. All eight stages of development in Erikson’s psychological theory are presented in the table below. The leftmost column lists the stages; the second column indicates the approximate age of their onset; the third contrasts the positive and negative components of each stage; the far right column lists the strengths of the Self or its virtues acquired through the successful resolution of each crisis. In accordance with the principle of epigenesis, each stage is based on the resolution and understanding of previous psychosocial conflicts. Erikson put forward the assumption that all crises, to one degree or another, take place from the very beginning of the postnatal period of human life, and for each of them there is a priority time of onset in the genetically determined sequence of development.

Eight stages of psychosocial development

Stage	Age	Psychosocial crisis	Strengths
Infancy (oral-sensory)	Birth - 1 year	Basal trust – basal distrust	Nadezhda
Early childhood (musculo-anal)	1 - 3 years	Autonomy - shame and doubt	Willpower
Age of play (loco-motor-genital)	3 - 6 years	Initiative - guilt	Goal
School age (latent)	6 - 12 years	Hard work - inferiority	Competence
Youth (adolescence)	12 - 19 years	Ego-identity - role confusion	Loyalty

Early maturity 20 - 25 years old Intimacy - isolation Love
Average maturity 26 - 64 years Productivity - stagnation Caring
Late adulthood 65 years - death Ego integration - despair Wisdom

While Erickson believes that the eight stages represent a universal feature of human development, he points to cultural differences in the ways in which each stage deals with problems. For example, the ritual of initiation into a young man exists in all cultures, but varies very widely both in the form of its implementation and in its impact on a person. Moreover, Erikson believes that in every culture there is a "crucial coordination" between the development of the individual and his social environment. We are talking about coordination, which he calls the "gear wheel of life cycles" - the law of coordinated development, according to which society provides assistance and support to a developing individual exactly when she especially needs it. Thus, from Erikson's point of view, the needs and opportunities of generations are intertwined. This complex pattern of reciprocal intergenerational dependence is reflected in his concept of interdependence.

Personality Development: Psychosocial Stages As noted earlier, Erikson believes that personality development occurs throughout a person's life. His analysis of socialization is best presented by describing the distinctive features of eight stages of psychosocial development.

1. **Infancy: basal trust-basal mistrust** the first psychosocial stage corresponds to the oral stage according to Freud and covers the first year of life. According to Erikson, during this period the cornerstone of the formation of a healthy personality is a general sense of trust; other scientists call the same characteristic "confidence." An infant with a basic sense of "inner certainty" perceives the social world as a safe, stable place and people as caring and reliable. This sense of certainty is only partially recognized during infancy. According to Erikson, the degree to which a child develops a sense of trust in other people and the world depends on the quality of maternal care he receives. "I believe that mothers develop a sense of trust in their children through treatment, which at its core consists of sensitive concern for the individual needs of the child and a strong sense that she herself is a person who can be trusted in the sense of the word "trust." "that exists in a given culture in relation to a given style of life. This lays the foundation for the child to feel "all is well"; to develop a sense of identity; to become what others hope he will become" (Erikson, 1963a, p. 249).

Thus, the feeling of trust does not depend on the amount of food or on the manifestations of parental affection; rather, it has to do with the mother's ability to convey to her child a sense of familiarity, permanence, and sameness of experience. Erickson also emphasizes that infants must trust not only the outer world, but also the inner world, they must learn to trust themselves, and especially they must acquire the ability to have their organs effectively cope with biological impulses. We observe similar behavior when the infant can tolerate the absence of the mother without undue distress and anxiety about "separation" from her. The question of what causes the first important psychological crisis is deeply analyzed by Erickson. He connects this crisis with the quality of maternal care for the child - the cause of the crisis is the unreliability, failure of the mother and her rejection of the child. This contributes to the emergence of a psychosocial attitude of fear, suspicion and concern for his well-being. This attitude is aimed both at the world as a whole and at individual people; it will manifest itself in its entirety at later stages of personal development. Erikson also believes that feelings of mistrust may increase when the child is no longer the mother's main focus; when she returns to those activities that she left during pregnancy (say, resuming an interrupted career), or gives birth to her next child. Finally, parents who adhere to opposing principles and methods of education, or who feel insecure in the role of parents, or whose value system is in conflict with the generally accepted lifestyle in a given culture, can create an atmosphere of uncertainty and ambiguity for the child, as a result of which he there is a feeling of mistrust. According to Erikson, the behavioral consequences of such dysfunctional development are acute depression in infants and paranoia in adults. The basic premise of psychosocial theory is that the trust-distrust crisis (or any other subsequent crisis) does not always find resolution during the first or second year of life. According to the epigenetic principle, the trust-distrust dilemma will appear again and again at each subsequent stage of development, although it is central to the period of infancy. Adequate resolution of the crisis of trust has important consequences for the development of the child's personality in the future. Strengthening trust in oneself and in the mother enables the child to endure states of frustration that he will inevitably experience during the next stages of his development. As Erikson notes, healthy infant development does not result solely from feelings of trust, but rather from a favorable balance of trust and mistrust. Understanding what not to trust is just as important as understanding what you should trust. This ability to anticipate danger and discomfort is also important for coping with reality and for effective decision making; Therefore, basal trust should not be interpreted in the context of an

achievement scale. Erikson stated that animals have an almost instinctive readiness to acquire psychosocial skills, while in humans psychosocial abilities are acquired through a learning process. Additionally, he argued that different cultures and social classes teach mothers to trust and mistrust in different ways. But the path to acquiring basal trust is inherently universal; a person trusts society just as he trusts his own mother, as if she is about to return and feed him the right food at the right time. The positive psychosocial quality acquired as a result of the successful resolution of the trust-distrust conflict is defined by Erickson as hope. In other words, trust passes into the infant's ability to hope, which, in turn, in an adult may form the basis of faith in accordance with any official form of religion. Hope, this first positive quality of the Self, supports a person's conviction in the significance and reliability of the common cultural space. Erikson emphasizes that when the institution of religion loses its tangible meaning for an individual, it becomes irrelevant, becomes obsolete, and perhaps even is replaced by other, more significant sources of faith and confidence in the future (for example, achievements in science, art, and social life).

2. Early childhood: independence - shame and doubt Acquiring a sense of basal trust prepares the ground for achieving a certain independence and self-control, avoiding feelings of shame, doubt and humiliation. This period corresponds to the anal stage, according to Freud, and continues during the second and third years of life. According to Erikson, a child, interacting with parents in the process of learning toilet behavior, discovers that parental control can be different: on the one hand, it can manifest itself as a form of care, on the other, as a destructive form of curbing and a preventive measure. The child also learns to distinguish between granting freedom like "let him try" and, on the contrary, connivance as a destructive form of getting rid of troubles. This stage becomes decisive for establishing the relationship between voluntariness and stubbornness. A sense of self-control without loss of self-esteem is an ontogenetic source of confidence in free choice; The feeling of being overly controlled by others and the simultaneous loss of self-control may give rise to a persistent tendency toward doubt and shame (Erikson, 1968b). Before this stage, children are almost completely dependent on caregivers. However, as they rapidly develop neuromuscular systems, speech, and social selectivity, they begin to explore and interact with their environment more independently. They are especially proud of their newly discovered locomotor skills and want to do everything themselves (such as washing, dressing and eating). We observe in them a great desire to explore objects and manipulate them, as well as an attitude towards their parents: "I myself" and "I am what I can." From Erikson's point of view, a satisfactory resolution of the

psychosocial crisis at this stage depends primarily on the willingness of parents to gradually give children the freedom to exercise control over their own actions. At the same time, he emphasizes that parents should unobtrusively but clearly limit the child in those areas of life that are potentially or actually dangerous both for the children themselves and for others. Independence does not mean that the child receives unlimited freedom.

Rather, it means that parents must keep the child's increasing ability to make choices within certain "degrees of freedom." Erikson views the child's experience of shame as something akin to anger directed at oneself when the child is not allowed to develop his independence and self-control. Shame can arise if parents are impatient, irritated and persistent in doing something for their children that they can do themselves; or, conversely, when parents expect their children to do something that they themselves are not yet able to do. Of course, every parent has at least once pushed their child to do something that actually lies beyond reasonable expectations. But only in those cases where the parents are constantly overprotective of the child or remain deaf to his needs, does he develop either a prevailing feeling of shame in front of others, or doubts about his ability to control the world around him and master himself. Instead of being confident and getting along with others, such children think that others are scrutinizing them, treating them with suspicion and disapproval; or they consider themselves completely unhappy. They have weak "willpower" - they give in to those who dominate or exploit them. As a result, such traits as self-doubt, humiliation and weakness of will are formed. According to Erikson, the child's acquisition of a constant sense of independence greatly strengthens his sense of trust. This interdependence of trust and autonomy can sometimes retard future mental development. For example, children with an unstable sense of trust may, at the stage of independence, become indecisive, timid, and may be afraid to defend their rights, so they will seek help and support from others. In adulthood, such people are most likely to develop obsessive-compulsive symptoms (which provide them with the necessary control) or paranoid fear of persecution. A social complement to independence is a system of law and order. Erickson uses the terms "law" and "order" regardless of possible emotional connotations. According to his theory, parents must always be fair and respect the rights and privileges of others if they want their children to be prepared to accept the limits of autonomy in adulthood.

"Willpower means the constant exercise of free choice, as well as self-restraint, despite the inevitable feelings of shame, doubt and irritation at being controlled by

someone. The source of goodwill is rooted in the discretion of parents, guided by respect for the spirit of the law" (Erikson, 1968b, p. 288).

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